

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON PHILOSOPHY AS A COMPONENT OF A SUBJECT BIBLIOGRAPHICAL RESOURCE**Sadigova S.***Azerbaijan (Baku)**Baku State University**Associate professor of document management department**Doctor of philosophy in history**<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4780-0163>***Abstract**

Philosophy is one of the components of socio-political science. This article discusses the complex of socio-political sciences and examines the problem of providing bibliographic resources for philosophy, which is one of the leading disciplines within this complex. Philosophy is the greatest achievement of human civilization, one of the oldest types of human knowledge. It is one of the oldest and most valuable areas of knowledge and spiritual culture of mankind. Philosophy is a special form of understanding the world and a system of views on the general problems of existence. In our country, when political, economic and social construction began after the restoration of independence, there has been a serious need for the philosophical study of reality. There has been a necessary need for the teaching and research of philosophy from a theoretical, methodological worldview and practical point of view. Because in the modern era, it is impossible to actively struggle for the implementation of these tasks without understanding and evaluating the essence of the tasks ahead from a philosophical-cognitive position. Bibliographic resources dedicated to the science of philosophy play an important role in this area. Thus, bibliographic studies, being a science that studies the structure and properties of bibliographic information, the processes of creating this information and delivering it to users, not only approaches these processes in general, but also studies the information needs of individual fields of science and activity, and the problems of studying that need.

Keywords: field bibliography, resources on philosophy, information consumer, informationized society, information provision.

Introduction

The decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the establishment of the State Commission on reforms in Azerbaijani science states: "The period of national independence has made it necessary to re-examine many issues related to the cultural and spiritual values of our people from the standpoint of the ideology of Azerbaijanism" [2]. Our libraries have a great responsibility in this area. As stated in the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On improving the activities of libraries in Azerbaijan", "Azerbaijani libraries are the national wealth of the Azerbaijani people. Our libraries play an indispensable role in collecting and preserving the valuable historical-cultural, literary-artistic and scientific-philosophical heritage created by our people, in passing on the achievements of human culture from generation to generation, and in increasing the intellectual and spiritual potential of our society" [1;3]. Philosophy is an important component of socio-political sciences. Unlike other socio-political sciences, philosophy is closely related to many sciences. For example, it is related to chemistry, biology, physics, mathematics, humanities, as well as socio-political sciences. Therefore, bibliographic sources are used when studying issues related to individual sciences in philosophy. As a result of the connection of philosophy with individual sciences, the publication of literature increases year by year. There are different groups of readers in relation to the publication of literature. In order to provide bibliographic support to readers, philosophy has various bibliographic sources.

Problem setting

The study of the problem of providing philosophy, one of the leading sciences of the socio-political sci-

ences and its bibliographic resources, is of great importance. It is known that modern bibliography has a number of areas in terms of object. Being a science that studies the structure and properties of bibliographic information, the processes of creating this information and delivering it to users, bibliography not only approaches these processes in general, but also studies the information needs of individual fields of science and activity, the problems of studying this need.

From this point of view, the bibliography of philosophy is closely related to a number of areas of special bibliography. As examples of these, it is possible to cite state bibliography, scientific-auxiliary bibliography, recommendation bibliography, universal bibliography, bibliographicization and bibliographic service. Indeed, books and articles on philosophy, like other fields of science, are also reflected in the sources of state bibliography. Scientific-auxiliary and recommendation bibliography, which are sections of special bibliography, are of great importance for the bibliography of philosophy.

The main part

In Azerbaijan, separate scientific institutions, departments and organizations, and libraries are closely involved in the organization and development of philosophical bibliography. Therefore, there are indicative sources of literature on the science of philosophy in Azerbaijan. In this regard, information publications are of great importance. A special section on philosophy is provided in the Azerbaijani Soviet Encyclopedia. For example, the philosophy section in volume IX is considered an important source in answering readers' questions about the science of philosophy. Here, materials on the history of the science of philosophy in Azerbai-

jan, literature publications, as well as the life and activities of philosophers (Heydar Huseynov, Firudin bey Kocharli, Mehbali Gasimov, Ziyeddin Goyushov, etc.) are provided.

We should note that in order to answer certain historical information and bibliographic queries, it is necessary to determine the methodology of compiling the encyclopedia, systematizing the materials, and also the main topic in order to study information related to philosophy, including socio-political sciences, in separate parts of information publications. Various types of queries are reflected within the main topic. General publications are also of great importance in the study of literature related to the science of philosophy. In this regard, Book I of Volume II of the "Book of Azerbaijan" is of great importance. A special section entitled "Philosophy-Social-Political Theory" is provided here. Within this section, scientific literature, educational literature, scientific-popular literature related to the science of philosophy published in the republic until the 1920s-1940s [6], literature on scientific institutions, publishing houses, institutes, societies, etc. engaged in this field is reflected. An important section is provided in the "Book of Azerbaijan" related to the science of philosophy. The study of literary publications during the period covered by Book I of Volume II of the "Book of Azerbaijan" requires a significant bibliographic search. Therefore, a general bibliographic index is of great importance in this field. An example of such a general bibliographic publication is the "Bibliography of Publications of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences" published by the MEK of the MEA of Azerbaijan. Book VI of Volume III of the index is devoted to history, economics and law [5].

The development of philosophy in our republic is associated with the name of the Institute of Philosophy and Law, one of the important leading institutions. In the early days, this institute operated as a special department of the academy. After the academy was organized in 1945, such a scientific research institution was established under the academy. The institute plays an important role in the training of philosophers in the republic, in the multiplication of literary publications, and in solving scientific problems in philosophy.

The role of that institute in the creation of the bibliographic index we mentioned is great. In the bibliographic index titled "Bibliography of Publications of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences", along with individual sciences, a special section on philosophy is provided. Within this section, it is possible to search for literature published by the institute after 1945. Therefore, all fields of science, including all literature on philosophy, are reflected in this important bibliographic publication of the academy. This bibliographic index reflects literature from different periods. A special section on literature on philosophy is provided in separate issues of the bibliographic index. It is necessary to note the services of the institute's scientists in creating a bibliography of literature related to philosophy.

A special bibliographic index has been published by the institute. For example, a bibliographic index entitled "Bibliography of works of Azerbaijani philosophers published in Moscow, Leningrad, etc. cities" has

been published. This bibliographic index covers the years 1970-1981. During this period, it is possible to study bibliographic information published in various scientific journals, collections, conference materials by Azerbaijani philosophers. Therefore, materials have been systematized in various sections related to the science of philosophy, for example, history of philosophy, dialectical materialism, ethics, aesthetics, logic, etc. on the basis of sections related to sciences [7;8;9]. Literature related to the history of other philosophical sciences related to individual philosophical sciences is reflected here. This bibliographic index is important in the dissemination of scientific works of employees of the scientific institution published outside the republic.

While the bibliographic index is important for readers, it also has certain shortcomings. For example, the lack of an introduction at the beginning of the bibliographic index is one of such shortcomings. Because the introduction introduces readers to the importance of the bibliographic index, its purpose and reader orientation, etc. issues. Therefore, an introduction should be written to such a bibliographic index. In the field of philosophy, the "Azerbaijan Encyclopedia" Publishing and Printing Union published the "Encyclopedic Dictionary of Philosophy" in 1997 with a volume of 520 pages [10].

This book, which is a necessary resource for university teachers, students and postgraduates, is useful for every reader who wants to expand their philosophical horizons, regardless of their specialty. The book contains concise articles on the history of philosophical thought, the main categories and concepts of philosophy, as well as the problems of dialectics, and the lives of world philosophers. Here, readers can obtain information about materials related to Eastern philosophy, the lives of thinkers and philosophers, and their teachings. The role of specialists in such an encyclopedia in providing information is undeniable.

The chairman of the scientific editorial board of the encyclopedia is Doctor of Philosophy, Professor I.A. Rustamov. Recent events in the world and in our country, current social processes, and the aggravation of political and ideological relations have set new and difficult tasks for philosophy, and necessitated an objective interpretation of the ways to solve its problems. The book contains articles on the scientific interpretation of the stages and problems of the historical development of philosophy, as well as many socio-political issues that have become even more relevant in connection with the current political situation. The dictionary also contains articles on the formation and activity of the philosophical and social thought of the Azerbaijani people. Articles dedicated to the biographies and teachings of the ideological movements of the Middle Ages, such as Zoroastrianism, Manichaeism, Mazdaism, etc., and their prominent representatives (Kind, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Ibn Rushd, Qutbuddin Razi, etc.) in different periods have also been included in the book. Unlike Western countries during the feudal period, non-religious philosophical teachings also functioned in the Muslim East along with scholasticism and mysticism. The dictionary also gives extensive space to Azerbaijani representatives of Eastern peripateticism (Bahmaniyar, Afsaladdin Xunaji, Sirjaddin Urmavi,

etc.), the creator of the pantheistic philosophy of Sufism Eynalguzzat Miyanachi, the founder of the philosophy of Ishraqi Shihabaddin Suhrawardi, and their followers. Suhrawardis, Tabrizis, Urmavis, Khoyls and other philosophers and thinkers, known for their affiliation with Azerbaijani cities, occupy a separate place in the book. A number of abbreviations, first adopted for reference publications, are promoted in the dictionary. The name of the article is replaced by the first letter in the text. For example, in the article "Aristotle", the letter A. is written instead of the full surname of the philosopher. If the name of the article consists of several words, then they are indicated in the text only by the first letters of the article.

For example, in the text of the article "Content and Form", instead of the full name, the names of articles with more than three words, such as M. and F., are indicated in the text only with the first letter of the article. All words and terms in italics in the articles indicate that there is a separate article about them in the dictionary. With the exception of the "Philosophy Dictionary" compiled by the prominent philosopher, academician Heydar Huseynov in the 1940s, the book is the first major dictionary published in this field in our native language. The development of philosophical knowledge from the perspective of new thinking was led by Prof. Izzet Rustamov.

The "Azerbaijan Encyclopedia" [10]. Publishing and Printing Union is confident that the "Philosophy Encyclopedic Dictionary" will play a positive role in the scientific-ideological field and will be useful for the rise of philosophical culture in our republic. Heydar Huseynov's scientific activity in the field of philosophy is highly commendable. Being the first prominent philosopher of Azerbaijan, he has made great contributions to the study of the history of Azerbaijani philosophical thought. In the bibliographic index "Heydar Huseynov" (1965) compiled by the library employee of the Academy, Ahmad Mahmudov [12], as well as in the bibliographic index published in the case of Heydar Huseynov, the main goal was to reflect all the works of the scientist. For this purpose, the author of the bibliographic index conducted extensive searches. He collected the rich heritage of the scientist by collecting H. Huseynov's published works on books, articles published in periodicals, reports and speeches. He published such a scientific auxiliary bibliographic index based on the materials he collected. The bibliographic index was given an extensive scientific introduction by the prominent literary critic of our republic, Mammad Arif Dadashzade.

The introduction was considered an important source for readers from a bibliographical and scientific point of view. Here, very rich information is provided regarding Heydar Huseynov's life and activities, student years, scientific, socio-political activities. The importance of the bibliographic index was extensively explained in the introduction written by the scientist to the bibliographic index. In the introductory part written by M. Dadashzadeh, one can learn various information about H. Huseynov. In the bibliographic index, H. Huseynov's works are systematized and described according to the years of publication. This is also im-

portant in terms of studying the history of the publication of the scientist's works. The bibliographic index consists of two parts according to the language in which the scientist's works were published: 1. Works in Azerbaijani; 2. Works published in Russian. As in part I, part II was also published according to the year of publication. In the bibliographic index, along with H. Huseynov's mainly scientific works, scientific articles should also be given. H. Huseynov played an important role in the public life of our republic. An auxiliary apparatus was created to facilitate the use of the bibliographic index. For example, an alphabetical index of the scientist's works. One of the bibliographic indexes is dedicated to the prominent philosopher Alexander Osipovich Makovelsky. He was the director of the Institute of Philosophy and Law of the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences (1945-1950). Makovelsky conducted fundamental research in the fields of the history of ancient Greek philosophy, dialectical and historical materialism, logic and the history of logic, pedagogy, psychology, especially in the field of Greek philosophy, sophists, pre-Socratic schools (Miletus and Pythagoras school; Heraclitus and his followers; Elea school, etc.), atomists (Leucippus, Democritus, Epicurus, etc.), translated a number of their works, and wrote commentaries on them. In his works on the history of philosophy of Azerbaijan, Makovelsky comprehensively studied issues such as Zoroastrianism, Avesta, Mazdaism, Peripateticism in the East, Neoplatonism and atomism, Sufism, "Ikhvan-as-Safa", "Nizami and his place in the East", 19th century social and philosophical thought, M.Sh. Vazeh, M.F. Akhundov. He also made a great contribution to the training of personnel in philosophy in Azerbaijan. The employee of the Central Scientific Library of the MEA, Syusorenkro, collected the scientist's works and compiled "A.O. Makovelski. Personal bibliographic index". The personal bibliographic index published about him plays an important role in the information provision of philosophical science. The bibliography of the works of Firudin Gasim oglu Kocharli, academician of the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences, Honored Scientist, prominent scholar in the history of Azerbaijani philosophy, covers the years 1950-1996 [11]. The index includes works published in Azerbaijani and Russian, as well as articles published in periodicals. The index, which was published in 1997 by the "Elm" publishing house in the series of Azerbaijani scientists and cultural figures, was compiled by Ch. Ahmadova, and the editor was F. Huseynova. The bibliographic index, prepared for publication by the "Elm" Editorial-Publishing and Printing Center of the Central Scientific Library of the MEA, contains 341 sources arranged chronologically. The index has the following sections: From the compiler; The main dates of his life, scientific-pedagogical and public activities; A short essay about his life and scientific activities (the author of the essay is Magsad Sattarov, a corresponding member of the MEA); Bibliography of his works (275 sources are reflected here); Works edited by him (42 titles in total); Scientific guidance and advisor to doctoral candidates (18 titles); Information about his life, scientific-pedagogical, public activities and works (7 titles) is arranged in chronological order. At the end of the index, an auxiliary device called "Alphabetical index of his

works”, “Alphabetical index of joint authors” and “Alphabetical index of authors who wrote about him” is provided. When looking at the “Bibliography of his works” section, it becomes clear that Firudin Kocharli’s first work was published in a periodical in 1948.

The index notes that Kocharli Firudin Gasim oglu He was born on December 8, 1920 in the village of Isali, Gadabay region, into a teacher’s family. After graduating from a 7-year village school, he continued his education at the pedagogical technical school in Kirovabad (Ganja) and worked as a teacher at the Isali village school, where he studied, between 1939 and 1945. In 1945, F. Kocharli entered the philosophy department opened under the history faculty of Azerbaijan State University. While still a student, F. Kocharli carried out extensive social work and soon became known as an active public figure. He headed the Student Scientific Society of the university, was elected chairman of the united local committee and a member of the party committee.

In March 1945, he successfully defended his candidate’s dissertation on the topic “Formation of the socialist culture of the Azerbaijani people”. From March 1954 to 1958, he worked as a senior lecturer and associate professor at the philosophy department of Azerbaijan State University. In our republic, there was not a single doctor of science in philosophy, except for academician A.O. Makovelski. In such circumstances, the leadership of philosophy at the Academy of Sciences of the Republic fell to F. Kocharli. It should be noted that in the 60s, the number of candidates of science and doctors increased significantly, and as a result, in 1968 it became possible to restore the Institute of Philosophy. Of course, F. Kocharli made a great contribution to the reorganization of the institute. He was appointed the first director of the Institute of Philosophy, whose activities were suspended in 1950 and were finally reorganized.

In June 1966, F. Kocharli defended his doctoral dissertation on the topic “Revolutionary democratic thought and Nariman Narimanov in Azerbaijan”, gave a scholarly speech about the features of the problem of revolutionary democracy in Azerbaijan, and brought full clarity to the formulation of the issue. In the index presented to the reader, the literature is arranged chronologically, and within each year, alphabetically. The bibliography of F. Kocharli’s works shows the main dates of his creative work, a brief description of his scientific research and organizational work. The index contains literature on the scientific guidance of dissertations, life and creativity of the scientist in separate sections.

The bibliographic reference book [14], dedicated to the world-famous Azerbaijani philosopher Shihabeddin Yahya Suhrawardi (1154-1191) reviews his life and creativity, provides information on extensive treatises, comments and footnotes written by prominent philosophers, and printed and manuscript copies of these works. Sources about Shihabeddin Suhrawardi, as well as studies in Eastern and Western languages, provide certain information about his world fame creates an image. The Presidium of the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences adopted a decision to celebrate the 800th anniversary of the death of Shihabeddin

Yahya Suhrawardi and prepared a plan of events. In this document dated April 2, 1991, it was decided to hold a scientific session in December 1991 in connection with the 800th anniversary of the death of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi; to publish articles about Shihabeddin Suhrawardi in the periodical press, in the newspaper “Science”, in the magazine “In the magazine “News”, to organize radio and television programs; to publish a monograph and bibliographic information about the life and work of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi; including proposals to obtain his works translated into the languages of European peoples, organize their translation, and prepare both the original and the translation of his works for publication; to announce a competition to create a portrait of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi; To perpetuate the memory of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi, a petition should be filed to name a street, square, and one of the scientific institutions in Baku; the Ministry of Public Education should be recommended to include sections dedicated to Shihabeddin Suhrawardi, along with other Azerbaijani philosophers, in the educational programs and textbooks of secondary schools.

The scientific and philosophical heritage of Shihabeddin Yahya Suhrawardi has always been in the center of attention of orientalist and philosophical historians. The 800th anniversary of his death according to the Hijri calendar was celebrated in Cairo, and a large collection was published on this occasion in 1974 (1975). Shihabeddin Yahya Suhrawardi has taken a worthy place in the development of human philosophical thought. It is our sacred duty to illuminate and promote his unparalleled service.

This booklet, prepared in a short time in connection with the anniversary of the world-famous Azerbaijani philosopher, will probably be further improved and expanded in future editions. The bibliographic index reflects the philosophical heritage of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi and its spread around the world; Addresses where the rich heritage is kept; Works of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi; Comments and footnotes to the works of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi; Sources about Shihabeddin Suhrawardi; Research on Shihabeddin Suhrawardi (20 titles in Arabic, 14 titles in Persian, 6 titles in French, 6 titles in German, 4 titles in English, 3 titles in Turkish, 30 titles in Azerbaijani, 8 titles in Russian). From the article entitled “The Philosophical Heritage of Shihabeddin Suhrawardi and Its Spread in the World”, it is known that Shihabeddin Abulfutuh Yahya ibn Habash Suhrawardi was born in the Suhraward settlement near the ancient city of Zanjan in Azerbaijan. At that time, Suhrawardi was famous for its natural beauty and prosperity, as well as for its cultural level. Bahaeddin Valad (...-1231), the father of Jalaluddin Rumi, especially noted this aspect. Prominent scholars, public and political figures came from Suhrawardi, who occupied a worthy place in the cultural history of the Near and Middle East countries. Shihabeddin Suhrawardi went to the city of Maragha at a young age, where he studied philosophy and the basics of fiqh (Muslim law) from Majaddin Jili. He then studied the book “Insights” (“al-Basir”) by the peripatetic philosopher Ibn Sahlan Sawin (...-1058) under Zahir al-Din Faraisi in Isfahan, which consists of sections on logic, metaphysics and physics

(natural science). Shihab al-Din Suhrawardi visited important cities in Azerbaijan and the Near and Middle East in general, including Ardabil, Miyana, Diyarbakir, Kharbut, Konya, Sivas, Mardin, Baghdad, Damascus and Aleppo. His main goal during those trips was to spread his original scientific and philosophical doctrines. His student Shams al-Din Shahrazuri (...-1250) wrote about this: "God sanctified his soul, (Shihab al-Din Suhrawardi) traveled to many countries, and showed a strong desire to find like-minded people in the sciences." Famous scholars and philosophers such as Ibn Yunus (1154-1242) in Mosul, Fakhraddin Mardini (...- 1195) in Mardin, and Seyfaddin Amidi (1156-1233) in other places fervently defended his ideas. One of the scholars who occupies a unique place in Azerbaijani philosophy, social ecology, and the study of mythological problems is Aghayar Shukurov. His articles, monographs, and textbooks are distinguished by their original research methods and methodologies, writing style, language, and generalization techniques. The problems he studies attract attention with their originality and relevance.

Novelty

Among the prominent scientists who have distinguished themselves among Azerbaijani philosophers at the modern stage with their productive activities and enriched the spiritual and cultural treasury of our people, Doctor of Philosophy, Professor Aghayar Shukurov has a special place. His comprehensive and extensive creativity should be studied in particular. His recent contributions to Azerbaijani science, that is, his research works, which have been met with special appreciation by our scientific community, are of great importance in the history of Azerbaijani public thought. In 2000, the Institute of Philosophy, Sociology and Law of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan published a bibliographic index dedicated to Aghayar Shukurov about the scientist [4].

The 107-page bibliographic index was compiled by Yadigar Babayev and Ariz Gozalov. The editor of the bibliographic index is Aflatun Amashov. This bibliographic index, which includes 169 bibliographic descriptions, includes the following: "From the compiler"; "The main dates of his life and scientific and social activities"; "Tired researcher" (the essay was written by Doctor of Philosophy, Veli Habiboglu); "Bibliography of his works" (18 books, 5 textbooks); "Articles published in scientific journals and collections" (83); "Newspaper articles" (43); "Candidate dissertations defended under his scientific supervision" (a total of 8 people) are presented in chronological order. In the "Reviews on Agayar Shukurov's books" section, it is possible to obtain information about the reviews of 13 authors. Finally, the search capabilities of the bibliographic source have been further enriched through the auxiliary indexes "Alphabetical index of his works"; "Alphabetical index of joint authors"; "Alphabetical index of authors who wrote about". The bibliographic index shows that Agayar Mahammad oglu Shukurov was born on March 25, 1946 in the village of Amankend, Bilasuvar region. He graduated from secondary school in 1963. Since childhood, he was interested in literature and history, and also wrote poems. At that time, due to certain obstacles, he entered the history faculty, not the

journalism faculty, for his exams. His diploma work on the topic "Social and philosophical views of Nasimi" was highly appreciated by specialists. In 1969, A. Shukurov entered the postgraduate course of the Institute of Philosophy and Law of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan. In 1975, he defended his dissertation on the topic "National and religious traditions" to receive the degree of candidate of philosophical sciences.

With his work "Socio-philosophical essence of global, ecological and demographic problems of the modern era", published in the "Elm" publishing house in 1984, he laid the foundation for a new direction of global problems in Azerbaijani philosophy. In 1989, A. Shukurov defended his doctoral dissertation entitled "The place and role of ecological problems in modern globalistics". In 1991, he created the "Philosophical problems of ecology" department for the first time in the USSR. Suffice it to say that by 2000, 24 issues of the journal "Ecology. Philosophy. Culture" were published on the initiative of the department. Professor Aghayar Shukurov participated and spoke at a number of international conferences. His works were published in Russia and Turkey. In the essay of the indicator titled "Tired Researcher", it is noted that if we look carefully at the books, monographs, textbooks, and articles written by him, we can clearly see the heartbeat and spiritual world of a scientist, intellectual, and citizen who deeply thinks about his people, homeland, and historical past. Since A. Shukurov's candidate dissertation was on the topic of "National and Religious Traditions," he studied the historical roots of religion, its true essence, its position in society, religious customs and traditions, and the problems of atheism in general in great depth. It should be noted that in Soviet society, special attention was paid to the study of religious customs and traditions, and the issues of atheism education. In this regard, the first published work of the young scientist was on that topic. In his book "Socialist Customs, Traditions and Atheism Education", published in 1979 by the "Bilik" society, he commented on important problems such as customs, traditions, their essence, the elimination of religious rites and ceremonies in the process of the formation of socialist customs and traditions, etc., and expressed certain considerations regarding the education of atheism.

It should be borne in mind that at that time there was a great need for conducting research of this kind. However, the young researcher did not approach the topics he wrote about the education of atheism from a dogmatic position at all; whenever he came to the right place, he also revealed the progressive features of religion, as well as the features that call people to fanaticism and superstition. We can find these aspects in the books "Islam-customs and traditions", "Social progress and atheism".

Conclusion

In the conditions of independence, the most important task facing our state and people, our scientists, intellectuals, and all kinds of specialists is to informatize modern Azerbaijani society. In general, informatization is a socio-economic and scientific-technical process that creates optimal conditions for meeting the information needs of members of society, state

administration bodies, local self-government bodies, all social structures of society, and public organizations on the basis of forming and using information resources, as well as implementing and organizing the rights of citizens in this area.

In modern times, the informatization of society requires further increasing the completeness, consistency and efficiency of current bibliographic information. Therefore, along with traditional publications, the creation of automated systems and the preparation of electronic publications are also necessary conditions of the time. Here, libraries and other subjects of bibliographic activity can directly participate in the formation of state and local information-library ideology, in the preparation of the legal basis of their activities. As a result, it should be noted that when studying the topic dedicated to the provision of bibliographic information on the science of philosophy, it became clear that bibliographic publications in this field are not enough. Therefore, in order to further improve the information provision of reader groups in the relevant field, it is advisable to increase the compilation of bibliographic indicators in this field, and at the same time, taking advantage of the application of modern information technologies, make their electronic version available to information users. The author's scientific articles dedicated to historical science and a number of topical topics have been published in journals published and indexed abroad [17-29].

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